

DEPENDENCE OF SIZE AND WEIGHT OF BLACK KARAKUL PELTS ON CONSTITUTIONAL TYPES IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE USTYURT PLATEAU

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15747231>

Abstract.

This article explores the dependence of the size and weight of black karakul pelts on constitutional types in the conditions of the Ustyurt Plateau. The study presents the transformation ratio of area and weight of freshly slaughtered pelts to those that have undergone primary processing, along with conclusions based on the findings.

Keywords: Ustyurt Plateau, black karakul, pelt size, weight, constitutional types, transformation

Introduction

In the harsh climatic conditions of the Ustyurt Plateau, it is relevant to study black karakul sheep by determining the productivity boundaries according to their constitutional types, based on their biological potential. Research aimed at increasing the pelt, wool, and meat productivity by applying selective breeding practices is of great importance [1. pp. 34–36].

The size and weight of the pelt significantly influence its grade. These indicators depend on several factors. During years with poor pasture and feed conditions, lambs tend to be born with lower body weight, resulting in smaller pelt areas. Conversely, with good nutrition, larger lambs are born, yielding larger pelts [2. pp. 35–36].

It has been proven that the size of a lamb's pelt is associated with the wool-constitutional type of the ewe. Ewes with a fine constitution give birth to lambs with relatively small pelts, while coarse-constitution ewes produce lambs with significantly larger pelts.

Several factors—such as the age of the ewe, her wool-constitutional type, the feeding conditions of karakul sheep, especially during the last stage of pregnancy, the fatness during lambing, and the selective breeding type of the animals—directly and significantly affect the development of the fetus's live weight and the formation of the pelt and wool cover [3. pp. 48–49].

Objective of the Study is to determine the size and weight boundaries of black karakul pelts based on the constitutional types of sheep in the Ustyurt Plateau conditions.

Object of Study: Samples of black karakul pelts.

Subject of Study: Size and weight indicators of black karakul pelts obtained from lambs of different constitutional types.

Research Methods: Generally accepted zootechnical, biological, technological, and statistical analysis methods were applied in the study. N.A. Plokhinsky's methods were used for determining "arithmetic mean (X), its error (Sx), and the coefficient of variation (Sv)."

Results

Our experiments aimed to determine the size and weight of black karakul pelts under Ustyurt Plateau pasture conditions. The obtained data are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 shows that the average area of freshly slaughtered pelts from coarse-type lambs was 1689.3 cm², from strong-type lambs it was 1613.8 cm², and from fine-type lambs it was 1487.6 cm² (p<0.001). Among the constitutional types, pelts from coarse-type lambs were 4.5% heavier than those from strong types, and 7.9% heavier than those from fine types (p<0.001). Thus, pelts from coarse-type lambs were the largest, while pelts from fine-type lambs were the smallest. The strong type occupied an intermediate position.

Regarding the ratio of salted pelt area to the area of freshly slaughtered pelts, coarse-type pelts lost 91.6% in area, strong types 90.2%, and fine types 88.7%, with fine types experiencing the least area loss—1.5% less than the strong type and 2.9% less than the coarse type (p<0.001).

Table 1 – Pelt Size and Weight Indicators

Indicators	Coarse Type (n=15)	Strong Type (n=15)	Fine Type (n=15)
Fresh pelt area, cm ²	1689.3 ± 94.5*	1613.8 ± 89.8	1487.6 ± 75.6*
Fresh pelt weight, g	872.5 ± 67.8	749.7 ± 67.4*	689.4 ± 55.7
Salted pelt area, cm ²	1547.4 ± 59.8*	1455.6 ± 74.7	1319.5 ± 69.3
Salted pelt weight, g	448.5 ± 37.2*	390.6 ± 26.2	363.3 ± 29.4*
Area retention ratio, %	91.6	90.2	88.7
Weight retention ratio, %	51.4	52.1	52.7
Weight per cm ² , g	0.29	0.27	0.27

*p<0.001

During the salting process, coarse-type pelts lost 48.6% of their original weight, while strong types lost 47.9% and fine types 47.3%.

Conclusion

Pelts obtained from coarse-constitution lambs were somewhat heavier, with a weight of 0.29 g per cm², while pelts from strong and fine types were both at 0.27 g/cm². Differences in thickness, density, and weight of the pelts are due to a variety of biological and environmental factors, which affect how pelts respond to processing.

These characteristics must be taken into account during the primary processing of black karakul pelts.

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